

BeOpen European forum and oBservatory for OPEN science in transport

Project Information

Url: www.beopen-project.eu

Project Coordinator: Centre for Research and Technology Hellas / Hellenic Institute of Transport

Coordinator Country: Greece

Project duration: 01/01/2019 - 30/06/2021

Funding Programme - H2020-EU.3.4. - SOCIETAL CHALLENGES - Smart, Green And Integrated Transport

Project mission

The overarching vision of BE OPEN is to create a common understanding on the practical impact of Open Science and to identify and put in place the mechanisms to make it a reality in transport research. Openness, transparency, fairness, reproducibility of science are key aspects around which BE OPEN seeks to establish the ground rules for the transport research communities, ultimately creating a community of transport research organisations willing to work on the basis of a commonly agreed “Open Science Code of Conduct”.

Type of synergy

Joint dissemination/communication activities

The projects have co-organised joint events to share the projects' results and reach a broader community. A practical example is coming from the organisation of the workshop “[Channeling open science for a sustainable management of the ocean](#)” as a side event of the Open Science FAIR 2021, that Blue-Cloud has done together with BE OPEN, Cos4Cloud and FNS-Cloud.